

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher; found in X documentation ...)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education; Youth work etc. See list Tab 2)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education; Youth work etc. See list Tab 2)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?
25.01.2018	Eurocarers homepage (no keywords)	Knowledge of researcher	http://www.eurocarers.org/it-is-time-for-italy-to-demonstrate-it-cares-for-its-carers	International organisa	Carer organisation	18 October 2017: Italian Senate's intention to examine a law proposal aiming to address the needs of informal carers.	National	-	-	http://senato.it/japp/bgt/showdoc/frame.jsp?tipdoc=So mmComm&leg=17	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	No more information on the new website identified	N
25.01.2018	Young Carers in Italia	Google search	http://europa.eu/youth/node/44154_it	Other	Other	-	International	-	-	http://www.carers.org/	Other	Other	-	Y
25.01.2018	Regione Emilia Romagna website	From letters of intent	http://sociale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/infanzia-adolescenza/approfondimenti/le-norme-e-gli-atti-in-vigore-1/le-norme-e-gli-atti-in-vigore	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	Collection of laws at regional level (not YC-specific). 1. Legge regionale n. 2/03 (Art.9) : http://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?turner=assemblealegislativa:legge:2003:2 2. Legge regionale n. 14/08 : http://demetra.regione.emilia-romagna.it/al/articolo?turner=assemblealegislativa:legge:2008:14	Regional	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29.01.2018	Anziani e non solo website	Partner organisation	www.anzianienonsolo.it/destinatari/giovanicaregiver/	NGO	?	-	National	-	-	www.giovanicaregiver.it	NGO	Advice websites for youth	New keyword: "giovanicaregiver"	Y
29.01.2018	www.giovanicaregiver.it	From anzianienonsolo.it	www.giovanicaregiver.it	NGO	Advice websites for youth	-	National	-	-	http://www.vita.it/it/article/2017/04/06/figli-badanti-e-sandwich-generation-a-che-punto-e-la-legge-sui-caregiver/142984/ Report "I giovani con responsabilità di cura in Italia" (Boccaletti, Mattioli & Mazzocchi)	News websites Papers on young carers	News websites Papers on young carers	New keyword: "giovanic con responsabilità di cura"	Y
29.01.2018	http://www.vita.it/it/article/2017/04/06/figli-badanti-e-sandwich-generation-a-che-punto-e-la-legge-sui-caregiver/142984/	From giovanicaregiver.it	http://www.vita.it/it/article/2017/04/06/figli-badanti-e-sandwich-generation-a-che-punto-e-la-legge-sui-caregiver/142984/	News website	News website	3 legal texts under examination: - 2048 (Cristina de Pietro): measures for people caring for elderly family members - 2128 (Laura Bignami): norms for the acknowledgement and support of the family caregiver - 2266 (Ignazio Angioni): national law for the acknowledgement and valorisation of the family caregiver	National	Loredana Ligabue (Anziani e non Solo, Associazione Carer)	She worked bottom-up at the first regional law in Emilia Romagna (legge regionale 28 marzo 2014, n. 2) that acknowledges family caregivers and at Ignazio Angioni's law proposal.	-	-	-	-	Y
29.01.2018	Report "I giovani con responsabilità di cura in Italia" (Boccaletti, Mattioli & Mazzocchi) (http://www.care2work.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Cover_report_care2work-IT.pdf)	From giovanicaregiver.it	Report "I giovani con responsabilità di cura in Italia" (Boccaletti, Mattioli & Mazzocchi) (http://www.care2work.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Cover_report_care2work-IT.pdf)	NGO	Papers on young carers	p. 7: YC not legally recognised p. 9: national law for secondary upper schools (Legge 10 dicembre 1997 , n. 425) pp. 9-10: national law comparing family members who work and study p. 10: conciliation support (legge 104/1992) and regional law for family caregivers in Emilia Romagna (legge regionale 28 marzo 2014 , n. 2)	National	-	-	-	-	-	New keywords: fratelli disabili, siblings, adolescenti caregiver, adolescenti che si prendono cura, figli di alcolisti, figli di tossicodipendenti, adolescenti	-
30.01.2018	legge regionale 28 marzo 2014, n.2	Mentioned in the report ("I giovani con responsabilità di cura in Italia")	https://www.spoole.ch/uri?ast&rect=1&q=&src=&source=web&cd=1&ved=0ahUKEwht2Qh027AlXWkDwKHfPECmDQFsg0MAA&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.care2work.org/	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	-	Regional	-	-	-	-	-	First and only Italian regional law about young carers	-
01.02.2018	Costituzione young carers Italia	Google search	Report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza in Italia" (www.gruppocrc.net/IMG/pdf/ixrapportocrc2016.pdf)	NGO	Youth organisations	Report on the implementation of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) in Italy (not YC-specific)	National	Arianna Saulini	Save the Children Italia, responsible for monitoring and advocacy	https://www.savethethechildren.it/	NGO	Youth organisations	-	Y

								Silvia Taviani	Save the Children Italia, policy officer. Psychologist -> WP3?	www.minori.it	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	-	
										www.parlamento.it	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	Y
										www.garanteinfanzia.org/	?	Youth organisations	-	Y
01.02.2018	Save the Children Italia	Found in Report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza"	https://www.savethechildren.it	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	Antonella Inverno	Policy and Law responsible	-	-	-	-	-
05.02.2018	www.minori.it (Centro Nazionale di documentazione e analisi per l'infanzia e l'adolescenza)	Found in Report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza"	www.minori.it	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	legge regionale 28 marzo 2014, n.2	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
05.02.2018	www.parlamento.it	Found in Report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza"	www.parlamento.it	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
05.02.2018	www.garanteinfanzia.org/	Found in Report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza"	www.garanteinfanzia.org/	?	Youth organisations	-	National	Filomena Albano	Judge in Rome and representative of the organisation. But not specific knowledge about YC and maybe too difficult to have an interview with her?	-	-	-	Organisation protecting children rights	-
06.02.2018	Comip Italia	Found on Twitter	http://www.comip.it	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	Stefania Buoni	She was a YC and in 2017 she founded COMIP, the first Italian organisation for children of mentally ill parents -> WP3?	http://www.mybluebox.it/	NGO	Youth organisations	First organisation for children of mentally ill parents in Italy. New keyword: "figli di genitori con disturbo mentale"	Y
06.02.2018	http://www.mybluebox.it/	From Comip Italia	http://www.mybluebox.it/	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	Stefania Buoni	-	-	-	-	Collection of projects, resources and information for children of parents with mental illness	-
06.02.2018								Livia Pomodoro	Judge and ex President of the Court for Minors of Milan	-	-	-	-	-
06.02.2018	http://www.care2work.org/	From http://europa.eu/youth/hode/44154_it	http://www.care2work.org/	International organisation	Other	Care2Work: youth-led initiative which gives a voice to experiences of young carers (running in Italy, Sweden, UK and Greece)	International	-	-	-	-	-	Project organised in collaboration with 'Anziani e non solo' and IARS (UK)	-
06.02.2018	Isoredana Ugabue	Expert identified on www.vita.it	http://www.caregiverfamiliare.it/?page_id=665	?	?	Collection of advancements in developing a national law protecting care givers (not YC-specific).	National	-	-	www.anzianienonolo.it	NGO	?	-	N

06.02.2018	Arianna Saulini	Expert identified in report "I diritti dell'infanzia e dell'adolescenza in Italia"	http://it.didattica.unipd.it/	Research institute	Research institute	-	National	Arianna Saulini	Teaching a Master level course entitled "Children's rights"	-	-	-	-	-	-
06.02.2018	legislazione giovani caregivers	Google search	http://www.caregiverfamiliare.it/	?	?	Collection of advancements in developing a national law protecting care givers (not YC-specific).	National	-	-	www.anzianienonolo.it	NGO	?	-	-	N
06.02.2018	legislazione giovani caregivers	Google search	http://www.anzianienonolo.it/legge-quadro-nazionale-per-il-riconoscimento-del-caregiver-familiare/	NGO	?	-	National	-	-	www.giovanicaregiver.it	NGO	Advice websites for youth	New keyword: "giovani caregiver"	-	-
06.02.2018	legislazione giovani caregivers	Google search	http://www.regione.emilia-romagna.it/notizie/2017/aprile/welfare-riconoscimento-giuridico-dei-caregiver-emilia-romagna-sprista-della-legge-2017-04-11	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	Other regions, e.g. Abruzzo, Campania, Lazio, Marche Piemonte and Sardegna, intend to adopt a regional law recognising and protecting caregivers like the one in Emilia Romagna.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
06.02.2018	legislazione giovani caregivers	Google search	http://www.felicitapubblica.it/2018/01/11/avanti-tutta-con-il-sociale-caregiver-familiare-e-legge/	News website	News website	Legge di Bilancio 2018: family caregivers recognised at the national level	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
07.02.2018	Legislazione young carers Italia	Google search	https://web.uniroma1.it/disse/sites/default/files/SemPer_Carini.pdf	Research institute	Research institute	In Italy there is no national policy supporting family caregivers.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Written in 2009	-
07.02.2018	Adolescent young carers Italia	Google search	eurocarers.org	International organisation	Carer organisation	18 October 2017: Italian Senate's intention to examine a law proposal aiming to address the needs of informal carers.	National	-	-	http://senato.it/japp/bgt/showdoc/frame.jsp?tipodoc=So mmComm&leg=17&id=01044834&part=doc_dc-allegato_a:1&parse=1	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	No more information on the new website identified	N	-
07.02.2018	Adolescent young carers Italia	Google search	http://www.mybluebox.it	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Collection of projects, resources and information for children of parents with mental illness	-
07.02.2018	Norme di legge young carers Italia	Google search	eurocarers.org	International organisation	Carer organisation	18 October 2017: Italian Senate's intention to examine a law proposal aiming to address the needs of informal carers.	National	-	-	http://senato.it/japp/bgt/showdoc/frame.jsp?tipodoc=So mmComm&leg=17&id=01044834&part=doc_dc-allegato_a:1&parse=1	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	No more information on the new website identified	N	-
07.02.2018	Norme di legge young carers Italia	Google search	http://www.redattoresociale.it/Notiziario/Articolo/504671/Caregiver-familiare-si-va-verso-il-riconoscimento-Le-proposte-di-legge	News website	News website	3 proposals for a national law for recognising family caregivers: - "Disposizioni per il riconoscimento e il sostegno dell'attività di cura e assistenza familiare" (Edoardo Patriarca & Ignazio Angioni) - "Norme per il riconoscimento ed il sostegno del caregiver familiare" (Laura Bignamini) - "Disposizioni per il riconoscimento e il sostegno dell'attività di cura e assistenza" (Vanna Iori)	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Published on 5th April 2016	-
07.02.2018	Disposizioni legali young carers Italia	Google search	http://www.care2work.org/	Other	Other	Care2Work: youth-led initiative which gives a voice to experiences of young carers (running in Italy, Sweden, UK and Greece)	International	-	-	-	-	-	-	Project organised in collaboration with 'Anziani e non solo' and IARS (UK)	-
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	http://www.caregiverfamiliare.it/	?	?	Collection of advancements in developing a national law protecting care givers (not YC-specific)	National	-	-	www.anzianienonolo.it	NGO	?	-	-	N
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	http://www.vita.it/it/article/2017/07/26/caregiver-familiari-lemilia-romagna-va-avanti-mentre-la-legge-nazionale/144143/	News website	News website	In the Senate, a national law recognising the figure of the family caregiver is still under examination. Emilia Romagna has developed some guidelines based on the first regional law protecting family caregivers.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	www.anzianienonsoio.it/	NGO	?	-	National	-	-	www.giovanicaregiver.it/	NGO	Advice websites for youth	New keyword: "giovani caregiver"	Y
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	http://www.secondowellfare.it/primowellfare/bignami-ora-i-caregiver-familiari-sono-riconosciuti-anche-in-italia.html	Research institute	Research institute	-	National	Laura Bignami	Senator, proposing a national law recognising family caregivers. --> Not YC-specific and maybe too difficult to have an interview with her?	-	-	-	-	-
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	www.youngadultcarers.eu/docs/ToYAC%20Booklet%202014_ITALIAND.pdf	Papers on young carers	Papers on young carers	-	National	-	-	http://www.siblings.it/	NGO	Disability	-	Y
08.02.2018	http://www.siblings.it/	From youngadultcarers.eu	http://www.siblings.it/	NGO	Disability	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	https://www.studio.cataldi.it/articoli/27480-caregiver-in-arrivo-fino-a-1900-euro-per-chi-assiste-un-familiare-disabile.asp	News website	News website	3 legal texts under examination for recognising and supporting YC	National	Valeria Zeppilli	Lawyer and PhD candidate. She wrote this article	-	-	-	-	-
08.02.2018	Giovani caregivers in Italia	Google search	http://www.lavorosociale.com/archivio/n/articolo/minori-assistenti-dei-minori	Other	Other	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	New keyword: "Minori assistenti dei genitori"	-
08.02.2018	Norme di legge giovani con responsabilità di cura Italia	Google search	http://www.salute.gov.it/portale/temi/p2_6.jsp?lingua=italiano&id=1936&area=salute&Bambino&menu=scuola	Government website (National)	Health	Legge n.176 del 27/5/1991: the state must "provide the child with the protection and care necessary for his well-being and ensure that the functioning of the institutions, services and institutions that bear the responsibility of the children and that they provide for their protection is in accordance with the rules established by the competent authorities in particular in safety and health".	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
08.02.2018	Policy famiglie fragili	Google search	https://www.aibi.it/ta/napoli-genitoriaita-supporto-alle-famiglie-fragili-e-promozione-benessere-dei-bambini-ecco-le-priorita-del	NGO	Youth organisations	Regional regulation: The interventions of protection, protection and promotion of children's well-being can not disregard the implementation of a comprehensive system of actions aimed at ensuring their fundamental right to live with their family, enshrined in the Convention on the Rights of the Child and by national and international legislation.	Regional	-	-	-	-	-	Not YC-specific, but for the protection of children	-
08.02.2018	Protezione young carers Italia	Google search	http://www.mybluebox.it	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	Collection of projects, resources and information for children of parents with mental illness	-
09.02.2018	Genitori con disturbi mentali	Google search	http://csvnet.it/notizie/le-notizie/istituzioni/144-notizie/2795-genitori-con-disturbi-mentali-nasce-la-prima-associazione-dei-italiani	NGO	Social care	-	National	Stefania Buoni	-	-	-	-	-	-
09.02.2018	Genitori con disturbi mentali	Google search	http://www.compitalia.org/	NGO	Youth organisations	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	New keyword: "bambini invisibili"	-
09.02.2018	Genitori con disturbi mentali	Google search	https://www.openstarts.units.it/bitstream/10077/8485/1/UGolini_tigor-VIII.pdf	Papers on young carers	Papers on young carers	Paper presenting the legislation about: (1) the protection of children of mentally ill parents; (2) the right to have a healthy childhood; and (3) the right of mentally ill patients to be parents and to have a family.	National	-	-	-	-	-	Written in 2012	-
09.02.2018	Diritti dei giovani caregivers Italia	Google search	http://www.secondowellfare.it/primowellfare/bignami-ora-i-caregiver-familiari-sono-riconosciuti-anche-in-italia.html	Research institute	Research institute	-	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

09.02.2018	Politica giovani caregivers Italia	Google search	https://www.ag.it/politica/chi_sono_i_caregiver_e_perch_la_manovrastanzia_per_loro_60_milioni_di_euro-3170077/news/2017.11.28/	News website	News website	Family caregivers will receive a state subsidy. From Laura Bignami's proposal, a fund with an initial budget of 20 million euro a year has been established.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
09.02.2018	Linee guida giovani caregivers Italia	Google search	http://colibrimagazine.it/sociale-e-servizi/caregiver-familiare-riconoscimento-sostegno-dalla-regione-molise/	News website	News website	Molise region published "guidelines for the recognition and support of family caregivers"	Regional	-	-	-	-	-	-	-